

Energy Absorption of Composite Materials under Crash Conditions

D. Hull

Department of Metallurgy and Materials Science, The University of Liverpool, P.O. Box 147, Liverpool L69 3BX, U.K.

ABSTRACT

A wide range of polymer-based fibre composite materials have been fabricated into tubes and tested at speeds up to 4 m/s in axial compression using a long stroke servo-hydraulic machine. Particular attention has been given to the controlled collapse of tubes to achieve optimum deceleration under crash conditions. The mechanisms of collapse are strongly dependent on material variables such as fibre and matrix type, fibre alignment in short fibre materials and lay-up sequence in laminated structures. There are corresponding variations in the energy absorbing mechanisms and in the total energy absorbed in the collapse process. Supplementary experiments at impact speeds up to 12 m/s suggest that the failure modes of several of the materials tested do not change significantly at higher speeds.

1. INTRODUCTION

The response of a structure to a collision with a rigid body involves a large number of complex interactions(1). Research in this field is often restricted to a consideration of the behaviour of simple shapes made from metals. Particular attention has been given to the axial collapse of thin walled tubes under compression and a fairly complete understanding of the processes involved is now available (2). For a given material the mode of collapse depends on the ratio of the tube diameter to wall thickness. Thus, thick walled tubes tend to form axisymmetrical folds in the tube wall (Figure 1) whereas thinner walled tubes develop an hexagonal or diamond fold geometry. An important characteristic of the collapse process is that it initiates at one end and develops progressively by formation of new folds adjacent to the original folds (Figure 1). The load-displacement curve for this behaviour has a characteristic shape (Figure 2). Formation of the first fold requires a much higher load than subsequent folds and the variations in load are associated with the development of the folds during collapse.

This type of response has been observed in metal and thermoplastic tubes and involves large amounts of plastic deformation. Johnson, Soden and Al-Hassani (2) have shown that the formation of the folds is associated with plastic hinges which travel through the material as the fold collapses. Large amounts of energy are absorbed in the collapse and folding provides an efficient method of

protecting structures, particularly vehicles, from the most severe effects of high speed impact. The capacity of a material to absorb energy in this way can be expressed in terms of the volume of material which has undergone collapse. Considering Figures 1 and 2 and noting that following fold formation the material in the folds undergoes the full extent of deformation the volume of material involved when the upper face is displaced from L_0 to L_1 is approximately

$$V = \frac{\pi}{4} (D_1^2 - D_0^2) (L_0 - L_2) \quad (1)$$

The energy absorbed is the work done in the collapse process which can be determined from the area under the corresponding load-displacement curve

$$W = \int_{L_0}^{L_1} p dL \quad (2)$$

The specific energy W_S , defined as the energy absorbed per unit mass is

$$W_S = \frac{W}{V\rho} \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the density of the material.

For a tube, which collapses progressively by the repeated folding mechanism, W_S will be independent of the total displacement except for the initial stages associated with the peak load. However, since the geometrical form of the collapse depends on the shape and dimensions of the tube, W_S is not an independent material constant. Some of the relevant parameters have been reviewed by Magee and Thornton (3) and some typical values of W_S obtained as part of the present work are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Values of W_S for Metals and Thermoplastics

Material	Displacement Speed, mm/s	Mode of Collapse	Specific Energy, W_S J/g
Polycarbonate	4	square diamond	15
	2000	square diamond	24
	4000	square diamond	15
PVC	4	square diamond	12
	4000	brittle	-
ABS	2	square diamond	8
Mild steel	4	hexagonal	29
	4000	hexagonal	25
Aluminium	8	axisymmetric	11
	1000	square diamond	16

2. COLLAPSE OF TUBES MADE FROM FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTICS

Unlike metals and thermoplastics, fibre reinforced plastics do not undergo large amounts of plastic deformation. The reinforcing fibres have strains to failure in the range 1 to 3% and the polyester and epoxy resins used in most structural applications have strains to failure in tension in the range 2 to 4%. Much higher strains to failure of the resins can be obtained in compression but

it is unlikely that these strains are achieved in composite structures. Thus, composite materials fail in an essentially brittle mode. This does not necessarily mean that there is a low resistance to crack growth because there are a multitude of microfracture processes which can occur in a composite material to absorb the elastic energy released by a growing crack. In fact many composite materials are notch insensitive even though the fracture mode is brittle. One of the objectives of this work was to evaluate the possibility of achieving multiple microfracture as a bulk material response rather than in the local region at a crack tip.

In some preliminary experiments it was found that two distinctly different modes of failure are possible. These are illustrated schematically in Figure 3. In the first mode, failure has started in the central part of the tube and has resulted in complete fracture. As will be described later the mechanism involved in failure depends on the type of material, but this mode is common to most brittle materials. A typical load-displacement curve for such a failure is shown in curve a (Figure 4). The high axial compressive loads lead to fracture in the 'elastic range' and the load falls almost to zero when fracture occurs. The small post-fracture crushing load, shown in curve a (Figure 4), occurs in tubes which stay aligned after fracture has occurred. The majority of the work done before fracture is elastic and the whole tube is involved in failure. The specific energy will be

$$W_S = \frac{4W}{\pi(D_2^2 - D_1^2) L_o \rho} \quad (4)$$

which is usually relatively small.

The second mode of failure, shown in Figure 3b, involves progressive crushing of the tube from one or both ends (4). Again the micromechanisms of failure depend on the material but in all cases the material is transformed in the crush zone from a rigid solid to a fragmented and friable solid by a multitude of microcracks. The load-displacement curve shown in curve b (Figure 4) has a linear elastic region followed by a plateau which is directly related to the crushed length of the tube. Crushing occurs at approximately constant load and progresses along the tube at the same speed as the cross-head of the testing machine. Neglecting the small amount of elastic energy, the specific energy is

$$W_S = \frac{4W}{\pi(D_2^2 - D_1^2) (L_o - L_3) \rho} = \frac{4\bar{P}_c}{\pi(D_2^2 - D_1^2) \rho} \quad (5)$$

This is potentially much larger than the specific energy absorbed in the first mode and is entirely dependent on the average crushing load \bar{P}_c .

The two modes of failure can be considered as competing processes since the initiation of one mode precludes the occurrence of the other. The active mode depends on the relative load required to initiate failure. In the example shown in Figure 4 the progressive crush mode has initiated at a lower load than the centre failure mode but once initiated has continued at a much higher load. Thornton (4) has shown that it is possible to trigger the progressive crush mode by bevelling the ends of the tube. The high stress at the bevelled end results in local crushing at loads below those required for centre failure. Local crushing can then propagate as a crush zone along the tube. The effectiveness of the 'trigger' mechanism varies from material to material.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

A servo-hydraulic testing machine with a maximum static loading capacity of 180 kN and a 300 mm stroke has been used for all the compression tests. The machine operates in displacement control in the range 4 mm/s to 4 m/s. The resisting force is measured using a strain gauge load cell of 250 kN measuring capacity and the test data is held in a transient data store.

The tubes were made by a variety of fabrication routes depending on the required fibre distribution and the fibre-resin system being investigated. These are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Methods of Fabricating Tubes of Composite Materials

Manufacturing Method	Resin-Fibre System	Fibre Arrangement	Approx. V_f
1. Filament winding	polyester-glass	helically wound fibres, angle-ply laminate	0.45
2. Wet tube rolling	polyester-glass epoxy-glass	woven cloth with weft or weave parallel to tube axis	0.5
3. Hot press moulding	polyester-glass (SMC) polyester-glass (DMC)	in-plane random chopped fibres partly aligned, in-plane random chopped fibres	0.3 0.15
4. Pre-preg tube rolling	epoxy-carbon (graphite) epoxy-glass epoxy-Kevlar	cross-ply laminate with one set of fibre parallel to tube axis	0.6
5. Pultrusion	polyester-glass	fibres aligned parallel to tube axis with additional layers of cross-ply and in-plane random fibres	0.5

The disintegration of the material in the crush zone was investigated using optical and scanning electron microscopy. Sections were cut from the crush zone and encapsulated in resin prior to preparation with standard diamond polishing compounds.

4. RESULTS

Centre Failure

This paper is concerned primarily with the progressive crush process. However, it is important to identify the alternative mode of collapse and in this section some examples of centre failure are described. Figure 5 shows the change in failure mode of high impact PVC tubes resulting from an increase in the cross-head speed. A similar effect occurs when the temperature is reduced. The axisymmetric or diamond-shaped plastic collapse from one end of the tube changes to brittle fracture involving catastrophic crack growth and the separation of the tube into large irregular shaped pieces. The tough-to-brittle transition is typical of all thermoplastic materials although the transition temperature varies widely.

Figure 6a shows the centre type failure in an SMC tube. The fibre volume fraction (V_f) was ~ 0.25 and the fibres were randomly oriented. Fracture resembled the fracture of brittle thermoplastics. Clearly, the high elastic stresses generated in the tube wall result in the formation of cracks which propagate at high speed in an unstable manner. This type of fracture occurs over a wide range of temperatures and cross-head speeds, presumably because the polyester resin matrix is a thermosetting polymer with a high heat distortion temperature. The load at failure is relatively insensitive to temperature and cross-head speed.

Two examples of somewhat less catastrophic centre failures in which the fracture appears to be dominated by the alignment of the fibres are illustrated

in Figures 6b and 6c. The tube in Figure 6b was made from woven cloth impregnated with epoxy resin ($V_f \approx 0.5$). Cracking initiated in the centre of the tube and was probably associated with local interlaminar splitting due to the buckling stresses generated in the tube wall by the axial compressive stresses. After a crack had formed across the wall of the tube the two halves of the tube interpenetrated each other and longitudinal tearing occurred parallel to one set of fibres in the woven cloth. The stress to maintain interpenetration was much smaller than the stress at the onset of fracture. The tube in Figure 6c was a $\pm 55^\circ$ polyester-glass fibre helically wound tube ($V_f = 0.5$). Fracture probably started by shear failure parallel to the fibres and was followed by interpenetration of the walls of the tube. The mechanism of interpenetration is more complex than in the woven cloth tube and sometimes involves splitting between the layers of the angle-ply.

A different form of centre failure is shown in Figure 6d for a polyester-glass pultruded tube with a high proportion of the fibres aligned parallel to the axis of the tube in the outer layers. Failure is dominated by fibre buckling and eventually fibre fracture occurs. Buckling is less pronounced when the proportion of axial fibres in the outer layers is reduced but the same type of failure mechanisms operate.

In all these examples the onset of failure is followed by a very sharp drop in load (Figure 4a). For some tubes some load can be supported during centre crushing and interpenetration but this is invariably much less than the peak load and it is clear that post-centre failure crushing offers little potential for energy absorption since only a small volume of the material is involved and the failure progresses by micromechanisms which require only small amounts of work.

Progressive Crush Failure

Although this failure mode sometimes developed in unbevelled tubes before centre failure the majority of the tests were made on tubes with a 30° to 50° bevel machined on one end. This ensured that failure started at one end although it did not always lead to progressive crushing.

Numerous types of progressive crush have been identified which can be broadly classified into (1) fibre splaying and bending (2) fibre splaying and axial tearing, and (3) micro-fragmentation, Figure 7. Some examples illustrating each form of failure are given in this paper. A more detailed investigation of the micromechanisms involved is currently being undertaken.

Examples of fibre splaying are illustrated in Figures 8a and 8b for polyester-glass tubes. The fibres are splayed out from the crush region and have partly folded into the centre of the tube and partly folded outwards. The orientation of the splayed fibres in Figure 8a is due primarily to the fact that they all lie at 55° to the axis of the tube. More regular splaying is shown by the $90,0,0,90$ tube in Figure 8b. The hoop fibres have fractured and the axial (0°) fibres splay out. Considerable breakdown of the wall of the tube occurs as illustrated by Figure 9 which is a SEM microsection through the crush zone. It is clear that many micromechanisms of fracture are involved. A schematic representation of splaying is given in Figure 7. The axial fibres bend through 90° at the compression plate and remain unbroken. After removal of the load on a partially crushed tube the fibres spring back elastically. A wedge of fragmented fibres has formed, at the compression plate, between the two main arms of the splayed fibres.

Fibre splaying and axial tearing is particularly well demonstrated in mica-shellac and paper-phenolic tubes made by tube rolling techniques. The mica or paper sheets form a continuous layer which is rolled on a mandrel and bonded by the resin. Tubes with up to 20 layers of mica or paper have been used. A typical crush zone of a mica-shellac tube is shown in Figure 8c. Initially, the layers splay to the outside and inside of the tube. The outside layers develop axial tears which extend to the crush zone and are regularly spaced around the tube wall, Figure 7b. Considerable delamination of the layers occurs as they

fold over. Fibre splaying and axial tearing are illustrated by the examples in Figures 8d and 8e for glass cloth-epoxy and carbon fibre-epoxy tubes respectively. The axial fibres splay out as illustrated in Figure 7a and the hoop fibres fail by axial tearing. A wedge of fragmented fibres is formed at the compression plate.

Micro-fragmentation is involved to some extent in all the examples mentioned above, particularly in relation to the fragmented fibres in the wedge. In some configurations and fibre-resin systems the entire tube wall can progressively collapse by micro-fragmentation. The example illustrated in Figure 8f for a DMC tube shows that the tube wall has broken down into fine particles.

The load-displacement curves for each of these crush processes are similar to curve b (Figure 4). The bevel on the end of the tube leads to the elimination of the large peak in the load shown by the centre failure tubes and subsequent crushing occurs at approximately constant load. The curves invariably show irregular serrations indicating sharp variations in the load as crushing progresses. The specific energy for crushing is readily obtained from the area under the load-displacement curves and the amount of cross-head movement (equation 5). The values of W_S , for the examples described above, are given in Table 3. As indicated in section 2 this supposes that the front of the crush zone moves at the same speed as the cross-head and that the width of the crush zone, L_4 in Figure 3, is constant throughout the crush. The latter point is difficult to determine because L_4 can only be measured in sectioned specimens. Microstructural studies on a series of similar tubes crushed to different lengths indicate that the appearance and width of the crush zone is independent of the extent of crush.

Table 3. Values of W_S for Composite Materials

Material	Displacement Speed, mm/s	Specific Energy, W_S J/g
Helically wound, $\pm 55^\circ$, glass-polyester	4	41
	4000	38
0/90 glass-polyester	4	65
	4000	55
Mica-shellac	1	25
Glass cloth-epoxy	4	58
	4000	65
0/90 carbon-epoxy	2000	56
DMC	2000	25
SMC	4000	37

An indirect measurement of the constancy of L_4 is obtained by measuring the position of the crush zone front and comparing it with the position of the cross-head. Some typical data are shown in Figure 10 for steel and DMC. Both tubes show an initiation period during which the crush zone is being established. The steel tube, which collapses by formation of plastic hinges, shows an oscillating response owing to the manner of hinge formation and growth. The average slope is 1 : 1.45 indicating that the collapse of a 1 cm length of tube involves plastic deformation of 1.45 cm of tube. In contrast, the slope of the curve for composite materials is close to 1 : 1 because the crushed material plays no further part in the fracture process.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper provides an introduction to an extensive investigation of the bulk energy absorption capacity of fibre reinforced polymer composites under crash conditions. The work is directed towards the use of composite materials for the structural parts of automobiles. To ensure that the passenger compartment does not experience extra high deceleration in a crash it is essential that the structure undergoes progressive crushing on impact. An important requirement is that progressive crush occurs at high speeds and a 'catapult' crash facility has been designed and built to test components at speeds up to 15 m/s (35 mph).

The types of progressive crush shown by the composite materials illustrated in Figure 8 occur over a wide range of crushing speeds indicating that the potential for energy absorption is not strain rate dependent. This is in marked contrast to thermoplastic materials (Figure 5) which behave as tough energy absorbing materials at low crushing speeds and as brittle glassy materials at high speeds. The specific energy absorption W_c of the composite materials investigated compares very favourably with those of steel and aluminium and there is every indication that values of W_c higher than those shown in Table 3 can be achieved by optimising the fibre type, arrangement and volume fraction.

The distinction between centre failure and progressive crushing highlights the importance of geometrical parameters on W_c and the overall performance of axisymmetric tubes in compression. However, it is the fibre arrangement which determines W_c in the progressive crushing mode. It is clear, from the limited results on crushing mechanisms presented here, that numerous fracture micro-mechanisms are involved. These include delamination, elastic bending, fibre fracture, compressive buckling, compressive shear fracture, transverse cracking, fibre pull-out and various resin fracture processes. The relative contribution of these mechanisms to the total energy absorbed has not yet been evaluated and there is the added possibility that considerable amounts of energy are absorbed in friction between the crushed end of the tube and the compression plate.

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Fig. 1 Axisymmetric collapse by plastic buckling
 (a) mild steel tube,
 (b) schematic representation.

Fig. 2 Force-displacement curve of a mild steel tube tested in axial compression. Collapse mode changed from axisymmetric to hexagonal folding at a displacement of 40 mm.

Fig. 3 Schematic representation of
 (a) centre failure,
 (b) end crushing.

Fig. 4 Force-displacement curves for a DMC tube (a) centre failure,
 (b) progressive crush failure.

Fig. 5 Failure of PVC tubes tested, in axial compression, at different cross-head speeds (a) 4 m/s, (b) 4 mm/s.

Fig. 6 Typical examples of centre failure,
 (a) SMC, 4 mm/s, (b) Woven cloth, 1 m/s,
 (c) Helicallly wound, 4 mm/s, (d) Pultruded, 4 mm/s.

Fig. 7 Schematic representation of progressive crush mechanisms for composite materials.

Fig. 9 Micrograph of a section through the crush zone in a glass-epoxy woven cloth tube.

Fig. 8 Typical examples of progressive crush fractures, (a) Helically wound glass-polyester, 4 m/s, (b) 0/90, glass-polyester, 4 m/s, (c) Mica-shellac laminated, 1 mm/s, (d) Woven cloth, glass-epoxy, 4 m/s, (e) Carbon-epoxy, 4 m/s, (f) DMC, 2 m/s.

Fig. 10 Comparison of position of cross-head and deformation front for mild steel and DMC tubes tested in axial compression.